

Incremental Learning through Fusion of Discrete Anomaly Models from Odometry Signals in Autonomous Agent Navigation

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Abstract—This paper presents a dynamic data-driven approach for efficient anomaly detection, extraction, and fusion of multiple heterogeneous anomaly models in a generative fashion. First, we propose an adaptive Bayesian filtering technique based on a combination of Null force hypothesis and Particle filtering to accurately track the trajectories of normal and abnormal cases. We then analyze the generalized vectors and clusters generated from adaptive filtering and sequential clustering procedures to effectively detect areas with high abnormalities. To achieve this, we use probabilistic distance measurements. Finally, to increase the agent’s vocabulary, we fuse different anomaly distributions to generate coupled anomaly models that allow the agent to have incremental learning capabilities. Our approach is completely data-driven and does not require any previous knowledge of the data or the environment. We show that our proposed method can effectively detect anomalies using low-dimensional odometry data and can eventually improve itself over time through iterative generation of fused anomaly models.

Index Terms—Anomaly detection, Adaptive Particle filtering, Generative model fusion, Incremental learning, Self-aware agent

I. INTRODUCTION AND RELATED WORKS

Modern-day autonomous agents and intelligent systems such as self-driving cars have the innate capability to observe their environment and respond accordingly by making various control decisions [1]. Advanced techniques have also been proposed to improve the safety and well-being of the car occupants [2]–[4]. However, to reach the levels of autonomy and consciousness which are comparable to human cognition, these artificial agents need an adaptive data-driven framework to improve their initial knowledge over time by learning from new experiences [5]. This crucial aspect is termed as incremental learning [6] and lies at the heart of the self-aware cognitive framework. Self-awareness allows an artificial agent to develop the capability to identify the shortcomings in its existing models compared to a dynamically changing environment through anomaly measurements. This way, it can improve its vocabulary of models in a generative manner to enhance its performance over time [7].

In general, for an autonomous agent to be recognized as a self-aware agent, certain essential capabilities are required. These include (a) model initialization, (b) memorization of internal states of the system, (c) inference of existing knowledge, (d) anomaly detection to measure changes in the environment compared to the existing models, (e) new model generation

to incorporate new knowledge, and (f) active decision making based on newly generated models [8], [9].

Achieving autonomous navigation and path planning of artificial agents, such as self-driving cars and mobile robots, is a key problem which has been widely discussed in the literature [10]. It involves the movement of an agent on a defined trajectory, from a point of origin to the point of the target inside the environment under consideration. It becomes even more challenging in the case of complex in-door settings or GPS-denied environments, where the global perception might not be available to the agent [11].

Anomaly detection is another field of research that has gained wide popularity due to its vast area of applications [12], [13]. Anomalies can be referred to as uncommon patterns in the data which deviate from the normal trends. Anomalies are also not absolute and depend on the type of data as well as the underlying data distributions, along with the expected outcomes of a certain system [14]. Similarly, depending on the types of anomalies, various anomaly detection methods exist in the literature including distance-based, classification-based, clustering-based, probabilistic and deep learning-based methods [12].

The main focus of this paper is on anomaly detection in low-dimensional trajectory data for autonomous ground vehicles. A lot of work has been carried out in this field, including studies related to autonomous navigation and path planning. For instance, in [15]–[17], authors propose probabilistic abnormality detection frameworks based on Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBNs) for autonomous ground-based navigation. Similarly, Slavic *et al.* [18] proposed a joint approach for anomaly detection in video data leveraging information from trajectory data using Markov Jump Particle Filters (MJPFs) and Kalman Variational Autoencoders. Nozari *et al.* [19] suggested an active Bayesian inference based framework for modeling autonomous vehicle decisions to account for anomalies in trajectory data. More recently, Liu *et al.* [20], came up with a robust trajectory prediction framework based on the Sparse Gaussian process. Similarly, Wang *et al.* [21], presented a hybrid approach for anomaly detection in autonomous vehicle trajectories using (Long Short Term Memory) LSTM based autoencoders and Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) utilizing the concept of free energy minimization. Shi *et al.* [22], formulated the problem of trajectory generation and anomaly

Fig. 1. Schematic block diagram of the overall incremental learning framework.

detection using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). Li *et al.* [23] and Min *et al.* [24], described interpretable and probabilistic anomaly detection frameworks for trajectory prediction based on transformer models. Extensive work has also been carried out on optimal trajectory planning for overtaking scenarios in autonomous ground vehicles [25], [26].

In self-aware systems, anomaly detection is a key step in distinguishing new experiences from the existing knowledge of the agent [27]. Once the gap between the existing and new experiences is realized, there is a need to combine the new information into existing models by generating new fused models to achieve incremental learning properties [28]. Fusion is also an important process in machine learning for combining the knowledge from different models to improve the overall performance of the system [29]. However, the fusion process and implementation of the incremental models is challenging due to the uncertainties as well as the dissimilarities involved in the data, observations, and the agent's states [30], [31].

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- We develop a dynamic and interpretable framework for robust anomaly detection in low-dimensional trajectory data using adaptive Bayesian filtering.
- We propose an efficient generative technique for fusing various anomaly models, making it possible for the agent to develop incremental learning capabilities.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the methodology, including the overall framework and the individual components involved. Section III discusses the experimental results and Section IV provides some conclusions along with future research directions.

II. METHODOLOGY

A detailed schematic block diagram of the proposed framework is shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that the overall

framework consists of various modules including the synthetic data generation module, followed by adaptive filtering and clustering modules, as well as anomaly extraction and fusion steps. The following sections provide an in-depth analysis of these modules.

A. Synthetic Data Generation

The goal of this module is to generate different variations of closed-loop 2D trajectory data with normal and abnormal sequences. The trajectories are generated using the concept of attractive and repulsive force fields as described in [32]. The attractive force field determines the direction of motion of the agent from one point to another, whereas the repulsive forces act as an obstacle, forcing the agent to take an abnormal trajectory to complete its path. We consider overtaking trajectories as abnormal sequences. The attractive and repulsive force field vectors are defined as in Eqs. (1) and (2), respectively.

$$F_{At}(\omega) = -\nabla(U_{At}(\omega)) = k_a(\omega_t - \omega) \quad (1)$$

$$F_{Rp}(\omega) = -\nabla(U_{Rp}(\omega)) \quad (2)$$

where ω and ω_t are the coordinates of the agent and the target point, respectively. U_{At} and U_{Rp} are the attractive and repulsive potential field functions and $-\nabla$ represents the negative gradient. For the case of repulsive force field the gradient can be computed using Eq. (3):

$$F_{Rp}(\omega) = \begin{cases} k_r \left(\frac{1}{d(\omega)} - \frac{1}{d_{max}} \right) \frac{1}{d(\omega)^2} \cdot \frac{\delta d(\omega)}{\delta \omega}, & d(\omega) \leq d_{max} \\ 0, & d(\omega) > d_{max} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where k_a and k_r are the respective force field coefficients. d_ω is the distance between the agent and the proposed obstacle, and d_{max} is the maximum impact extent of the obstacle.

Furthermore, to account for the uncertainties in the real-world environment, Gaussian noise is also added to the original trajectories.

B. Adaptive Bayesian Filtering

This module consists of two successive iterations of filtering as well as clustering, and depends on the initial state of the agent. In the case of the first experience, i.e., when no previous clusters or vocabulary exist, we use Null Force hypothesis, which is a special case of Kalman Filter [33] to perform filtering only considering the normal trajectory. Once the first iteration of filtering is completed, we perform sequential clustering to group the points into various clusters using distance measures. Eq. (4) shows the mathematical concept behind the generation of sequential clusters:

$$\begin{cases} d(x_i, C_k) > \theta, & C_{k+1} = x_i \\ \text{Otherwise,} & C_k \cup x_i \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where x_i is the current point, C_k is the k^{th} cluster, C_{k+1} is the next cluster and θ is the predefined threshold.

In the second iteration, the filtering is adaptive in the sense that the particle filter utilizes the clusters generated from the previous step along with the original over-taking trajectories to make predictions. The posterior probability (see [34]) is calculated using Eq. (5):

$$p(x_k | z_{1:k}) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} w_k^i \delta(x_k - x_k^i) \quad (5)$$

where N_s is the number of samples, x_k^i and w_k^i denote the i^{th} sample and the corresponding weight, respectively. δ represents the Dirac delta function.

Generalized vectors (GVs) pertaining to the normal and over-taking scenarios are produced as a result of the filtering step. GV's are derived as a result of computing the predictions, based on the hypothesis of a null force filter, i.e., assuming that there is no movement. By computing these vectors, which indicate how the prediction model is moving, we can extract information about the observed force field. GV's can also be considered as final errors that allow us to correct the prediction model. Finally, clustering is performed again to generate clusters for the abnormal trajectories.

C. Anomaly Extraction

Once we have obtained the generalized vectors and clusters for both normal and over-taking trajectories, they are compared using the Kullback Leibler (KL) divergence as defined by Eq. (6), to identify how the two distributions, p and q differ from one another.

$$D_{KL}(p||q) = \sum_i^k p_i \log \frac{p_i}{q_i} \quad (6)$$

The concept of Free Energy minimization is used to describe the detection of anomalies as discussed in [35]. For example, if the trajectory under consideration is far away from the normal trajectory, we say that the free energy of the system is high and this leads to the presence of an anomaly. Once the high

Fig. 2. Stages of closed loop trajectory generation: (a) direction of attractive force field (b) simple square trajectory, (c) normal trajectory with added noise and (d) abnormal trajectory with noise.

anomaly regions are identified, they are extracted from the rest of the trajectories. The vocabularies and transition matrices of the extracted anomalies are stored separately for further processing.

D. Anomaly Model Fusion

This module involves two discrete steps. The first step includes the proper alignment of different anomaly models with respect to one another. This is achieved by introducing geometric transformations including translation, rotation, and reflection. Once the anomalies are aligned, we proceed with the actual anomaly fusion using a strategy of adaptive summation. Initially we assess whether the two anomaly models are close together or not by computing the Kullback Leibler divergence between their probability distributions and comparing it with an adaptive threshold. We call this step the anomaly model classification (see Fig. 1). If it is determined that the two anomalies are close to each other, their probability distributions are added using approaches discussed in [36] to form a fused model which can characterize the individual anomaly models. The probability density function (PDF) of a Gaussian distribution is given by Eq. (7):

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

where μ is the mean and σ is the standard deviation of the distribution. The sum of two Gaussian distribution can be achieved through convolution of the two PDFs as show in Eq. (8):

$$f_z(t) = f_x * f_y = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_x(x) f_y(t - x) dx \quad (8)$$

The resulting distribution contains the aggregate of the respective means and variances of the initial PDFs. The fusion process is an incremental step to enhance the vocabulary of the agent, which can be iteratively used in the filtering steps, thus forming a closed loop of incremental learning. Fused anomaly

models also allow us to estimate the center as well as the radius of the repulsive force related to the anomalies.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section discusses in detail the intermediary results produced by each module of the proposed framework as well as the final anomaly model fusion results.

A. Data Generation Results

Fig. 2 shows different stages of trajectory generation including (a) the initial attractive force field used to generate the trajectory, (b) normal trajectory without noise, (c) normal trajectory with added Gaussian noise, and (d) abnormal trajectory with Gaussian noise. We generate two separate configurations of the closed loop trajectories, i.e., square and rhombus. Figs 3(a-d) and 4(a-d) show different variations of the overtaking scenarios for both configurations respectively. For illustration purposes, the results of subsequent steps are discussed only considering the scenarios shown in Fig 3(c) and 4(c), i.e., the bottom overtaking case of square configuration and south-west overtaking case of rhombus configuration, respectively.

Fig. 3. Overtaking scenarios in Square configuration: (a) Top overtaking, (b) Left overtaking, (c) bottom overtaking, (d) right overtaking.

Fig. 4. Overtaking scenarios in Rhombus configuration: (a) North-West overtaking, (b) South-East overtaking, (c) South-West overtaking, (d) North-East overtaking.

B. Adaptive Bayesian Filtering Results

Fig. 5(a-b) shows the results of the first iteration of filtering considering only the normal trajectories of both square and rhombus configurations. The figures include trajectory tracking results (left) and the generalized vectors generated as a result of the filtering (right). Fig. 6(a,b) displays the initial clusters generated after the 1st iteration of clustering.

Fig. 5. Results for 1st Iteration of Filtering. Trajectory tracking and generalized vectors for (a) Square and (b) Rhombus configuration.

Fig. 6. Initial clusters of (a) Square and (b) Rhombus configuration.

Similarly, Fig 7(a,b) shows the results of the second iteration of filtering including trajectory tracking and generalized vectors related to the overtaking scenarios. Fig. 8(a-d) illustrates the results of the second iteration of clustering including final clusters along with the detection of anomaly parts for both square and rhombus configurations, respectively. It can be seen in Fig. 8(b) and (c) that there are large spikes in red color compared to the blue ones between time instants of 0 and 50, signifying the occurrence of overtaking.

C. Anomaly Extraction Results

Fig. 9(a,b) demonstrates the results of the extraction of regions with high anomalies from the final clusters of both square and rhombus configurations, respectively. The vocabularies and transition matrices of these anomalies are stored separately for further processing. It can also be seen that there is a certain degree of rotation between both anomalies.

Fig. 7. Results for 2^{nd} Iteration of Filtering. Trajectory tracking and generalized vectors for (a) Square and (b) Rhombus configuration.

Fig. 8. Final clustering results for (a) Square and (b) Rhombus configuration.

Fig. 9. Anomaly extraction results: (a) Square and (b) Rhombus configuration.

D. Anomaly Fusion Results

Fig. 10 (a,b) shows the results of anomaly alignment which is a prerequisite step for actual anomaly fusion. It can be seen that the anomaly pertaining to the rhombus configuration has been adjusted through geometric rotation to align it with the anomaly that is present in the case of square configuration.

Finally, Fig. 11(a) shows the result of the fusion of both scenarios depicted in the Fig. 10. This is achieved by adding

Fig. 10. Anomaly alignment of (b) Rhombus with (a) Square configuration.

the Gaussian distributions of both anomalies to generate a fused model, depicting the new knowledge learned by the agent. Fig. 11(b) shows the estimated center as well as the radius of the repulsive force of the fused anomaly model.

Fig. 11. Fusion results: (a) fused anomaly, (b) fused anomaly with estimated repulsive force center and radius.

It can be deduced from Fig. 11 that the fused anomaly model is more accurate because it contains less amount of clusters as compared to the individual models observed in Fig. 10(a,b). Moreover, the fusion results also help us to estimate the center of the repulsive force by not only providing the mean trajectory but also taking into account the noisy variations which form the covariance part of the estimate.

TABLE I
EUCLIDEAN DISTANCES BETWEEN ESTIMATED CENTERS OF DIFFERENT ANOMALY MODELS AND THE INITIAL REPULSIVE FORCE CENTER.

Estimated Anomaly Centers	Initial Centers	Euclidean Distance	
Bottom OT Model	(22.5,2)	(25,0)	3.20
South-West OT Model	(14.5,-2)	(25,0)	10.69
Fused Anomaly Model	(24,1.5)	(25,0)	1.80

Table 1 shows the comparison of Euclidean distances of the estimated anomaly model centers with the center of the initial repulsive force. It can be seen that the Euclidean distance of the fused anomaly model (3rd row) is the smallest compared to the individual anomaly models. This also validates that our fused anomaly model is quantitatively closer to the original trajectory. This work is ongoing, as we are now trying to develop a probabilistic model evaluation framework based on the principle of Minimum Description Length (MDL) [37] to further evaluate our methodology in terms of generalization capabilities.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we address the problem of anomaly detection in low-dimensional trajectory data for autonomous agents, while improving the agent's knowledge over time through

incremental learning. Initially, we generate different scenarios of synthetic trajectory data using the concept of attractive and repulsive fields. After that, we propose an efficient probabilistic anomaly detection technique based on adaptive Bayesian filtering and free energy minimization principle to accurately localize and extract different anomaly models. Finally, we effectively fuse the anomalies to generate new models to be used by the agent for incremental learning purposes. In the future, we plan to develop a similar framework compatible with 3D trajectories for autonomous aerial vehicles, and to also detect anomalies in high-dimensional image and video data using similar techniques. We also plan to compare our proposed methodology with other state-of-the-art approaches, including the use of real-world datasets.

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